

MIAS Plugin Tutorial

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Mountain Legacy Project

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Step 1: Classification

The classification step uses an automated algorithm to create a landcover classification for the provided reference image. The result is referred to as a *mask*.

Downloading Models

PyLC models are downloadable from the PyLC GitHub page under the Pretrained Models section (file extension .pth). Separate models are required for greyscale and colour images.

Parameters

Input Image: the image to be classified.

Select Model: model file (.pth) downloaded in the previous step.

Scale (optional): between 0.1 and 1. PyLC will run faster using a reduced scale, but the classified image will be lower resolution.

Running and Saving

Click the Run button to create a classified image. This may take some time. The mask will not be saved until you click the Save button.

Step 2: Virtual Photograph Production

The goal of the virtual photograph is to produce a model of the reference image using elevation data. The virtual photograph should match the reference image as closely as possible.

Reference Data

Reference Image: the image to be replicated

DEM: a digital elevation model. VP production works better with a *digital surface model*.

Camera Parameters

This is where you input camera parameters corresponding to the reference image. Camera parameters can be saved or loaded as a text file.

Easting and Northing: the UTM coordinates for the camera location. The program will automatically read the correct UTM Zone based on the provided DEM.

Elevation: the elevation in meters of the camera. If left blank, the program will read the elevation from the provided the DEM.

Camera height: the height above ground-level that the camera was held or mounted for the photograph. Default is 1.6 m.

Azimuth: the direction the camera was facing (in degrees).

Field-of-View: the range observable through the camera in degrees.

Adjustments

The camera parameters can be adjusted using positional buttons. Click Generate after making adjustments to view the updated virtual photograph.

Running and Saving

Click the Generate button to make a virtual photograph. The image will not be saved until you click the Save button. You must also save the camera parameters as a text file before moving on.

Step 3: Alignment

The alignment step is used to align the classified image (mask) to the virtual photograph. It can also be used to align historical and repeat photograph.

Parameters

Source Image: the alignment will be applied to this image. Choose the original image (or in the case of repeat photography, choose the repeat image).

Destination Image: the source image is aligned to this image. Choose the virtual photograph (or in the case of repeat photography, choose the historical image).

Mask (optional): the classified image. Alignment will be applied to the mask.

Control Points

Use the tools to add or remove control points on the images. Control points can also be saved or loaded as a text file. A minimum of four control points is required.

Alignment

Press Align to apply the transformation. Use the Swipe tool to assess the accuracy. If the alignment is not good, choose the Undo button to reset the images while preserving the control points. Control point accuracy is displayed by RMSE in the table. Delete points with large RMSE.

Saving

Choose which image you would like to save (the reference image or the mask) from the menu in the top left. Click Save.

Step 4: Viewshed Production

This is the final step to create a georeferenced and classified raster representing the original image.

Parameters

DEM: a digital elevation model. Viewshed production works better with a *digital terrain model*.

Aligned Mask: the aligned and classified image from the previous step.

Camera Parameters: a text file containing the camera parameters that were used in Step 2 to create the virtual photograph.

Running and Saving

Click Run to produce the viewshed. The viewshed will not be saved until you click the Save button.